

Adding Symmetry Considerations to Newtonian Mechanics to Obtain Quantum Mechanics?

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Newtonian mechanics may be used to determine Snell's law in two dimensions as shown in (1). Specifically, one needs two concepts. The first is the conservation of momentum (an interaction variable) along the x-axis (and also $E=pc$ with E unchanged), if the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface lies in the x direction. The second is the trajectory of the photon because the incident and refracted angles are measured using the incident and refracted rays (trajectories) relative to the y axis. Given that this approach suffices to obtain Snell's law as shown in (1), one might consider the problem solved.

In this note, we consider that both the notion of a trajectory and conservation of momentum are required to obtain Snell's law. We suggest a formal approach which includes trajectory variables x,y,z and interaction variable p_x,p_y,p_z . Furthermore, we argue that symmetries in the problem must be respected. The first symmetry is rotational as one may rotate the co-ordinate axes. One may propose $p \cdot r$. In order to obtain p_x , one may use d/dx . In one dimension, $p_x = d/dx (x p_x) = p_x$ seems like a math trick, but in the case of $p \cdot r$, one includes rotational symmetry in the problem. The second symmetry, which we argue exists and is essential, is that of invariance along the straight line trajectory of the photon. Now $p \cdot r$ changes value along the trajectory and there is no sense whatsoever of any kind of invariance along the photon ray. One cannot change the fact that $p \cdot r$ is different at various trajectory points, but by constructing $\exp(i p \cdot r)$ one may at least show that the magnitude of this function is constant. We stress that one must somehow show invariance along the ray while respecting rotational invariance.

As a result, one may obtain Snell's law by showing that $p_x(\text{left side}) = d/dx \exp(-i p \cdot r)$ at $x=0^- = p_x(\text{right side}) = d/dx \exp(-i p \cdot r)$ at $x=0^+$. This approach may seem to be unnecessarily complicated, but it shows that $\exp(-i p_x x)$ is continuous along x as there is no interaction there.

We suggest that including essential symmetries as well as trajectory and interaction information (p vector) seems to be a general manner of describing the physics of the moving photon, yet in obtaining Snell's law, $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ does not yield any physics that is not present in the usual Newtonian approach (1). One might suggest that $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ a formality. This, however, proves not to be the case in one-dimensional reflection-refraction. In that case, making $\exp(ip_x x)$ continuous at an n_1 - n_2 junction (as well as its first derivative), one requires a reflected ray. This leads to two equations in two unknowns (a parameter for the reflected ray and another for the refracted, assuming a weight of 1 for the incident) which may be solved to yield the probability to reflect and refract, quantities which may not be obtained using Newtonian mechanics. Thus, we suggest that the consideration of important symmetries in the problem through the combination of the trajectory and interaction p vector is a more general approach than Newtonian mechanics, i.e. leads to quantum mechanics.

Snell's Law in Two Dimensions

Snell's law is:

$\sin(\theta_{\text{incident}}) / \sin(\theta_{\text{refracted}}) = n_2/n_1$ ((1)) where n_i is the index of refraction

The incident and refracted angles are measured between the incident and refracted trajectories and the y-axis and the n_1 - n_2 interface lies along the x-axis. Thus, one must be aware of the physical trajectory. At the same time, one may use conservation of momentum in the x-directions (as argued in (1)). This follows directly from Newtonian mechanics. From these two considerations (as well as $E=pc$ and E remains unchanged), one obtains ((1)). We note that in the above, the two considerations are presented independently, i.e. written as two independent statements. One must impose conservation of momentum directly rather than have it follow mathematically from some kind of continuity of a function which combines both trajectory and p vector information.

Combining Trajectory and Interaction Information

We suggest combining trajectory and interaction information as both are required to derive Snell's law. We seek an approach which allows for conservation of momentum to appear without having to explicitly impose it, through continuity of some function as an example. If one combines p vector and r vector, one should respect the symmetries present in the physical problem. We suggest that the first is rotational symmetry because one may rotate the co-ordinate axes in the x-y plane. We consider:

$P \cdot r$ ((2))

A second important symmetry is the invariance of points on the trajectory ray. Now $p \cdot r$ differs for different trajectory points and so one has a problem. One remedy is to consider:

$\exp(i p \cdot r)$ ((3))

Even though $p \cdot r$ changes for different trajectory points, its magnitude remains constant along the incident trajectory ray and the refracted.

Given that there is no force along the x-axis, one requires $p(\text{incident})_x = p(\text{refracted})_x$. Alternatively, one may consider $\exp(i p_x x)$ to be a continuous function which does not sense any changes as one moves along x. In this way, one does not need to explicitly know about conservation of momentum. One only needs to know that there is no force which changes p_x . From these ideas, as in the above paragraph, one may obtain Snell's law.

This second approach requires the form ((3)) which includes symmetries in the problem, but one obtains the same Snell's law as in the above paragraph. One may then consider ((3)) a formal approach which does not really yield any new information that is not already conveyed by Newtonian mechanics. One may show, however, that this is not the case for one dimensional reflection-refraction.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

We argue that ((3)) is a general expression including symmetries in the problem and the sense of conservation of momentum if one considers continuity. One dimensional reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 junction does not change the energy of the incident photon, i.e. the reflected and refracted photons have the same energy. From the point of view of energy, nothing changes except that one now has a reflected and refracted ray (on average). (Any single photon can either reflect or refract.). If one tries to apply continuity to $\exp(ipx)$ as well as its first derivative, one has:

$$A \exp(ip_1 x) + B \exp(-ip_1 x) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad p_2 = n_2 p \text{ and } p = n_1 p \text{ and}$$

$$A p_1 \exp(ip_1 x) - p_1 B \exp(-ip_1 x) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((3))$$

Here A is linked with the incident photon, B the reflected and C, the refracted. If $A=1$, one may solve for B and C. One may also show that:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \text{ where } c_1=c/n_1 \text{ and } c_2=c/n_2 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is equivalent to $1 = \text{Probability to reflect} + \text{Probability to refract}$ ((5)).

The point is that the values of these probabilities are calculable using the approach of ((3)), but not from Newtonian mechanics. We have already argued this in various previous notes. Here, we wish to suggest that the reason seems to be that Newtonian mechanics does not express the full symmetries in the problem. In particular, it is concerned with an interaction at $x=0$ and not with any invariance which might exist along the incident, reflected or refracted rays. This symmetry is directly linked to $\exp(ipx)$, which in turn yields the continuity approach required to obtain B and C and hence reflection and refraction probabilities. Thus, we suggest that it is this symmetry condition which imposes an extra constraint on the problem which is not present in Newtonian mechanics

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that a Newtonian approach which considers both trajectory and conservation of p_x (x component of momentum) in x - y space may be used to derive Snell's law as shown in (1). Here the n_1 - n_2 interface lies along x . We suggest that a general math approach should exist which combines trajectory (x, y, z) variables with interaction variables (p_x, p_y, p_z), but this seems to require respecting various physical symmetries present. In particular, one may rotate the co-ordinate axes, so one requires rotational symmetry provided by $p \cdot r$. The problem is that $p \cdot r$ has different values for different trajectory points (for both an incident and reflected ray). There should be some kind of invariance along these rays which at the same time incorporates $p \cdot r$. We suggest $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ as a solution). Continuity along the x axis, i.e

$\exp(i p x)$ leads to the notion of conservation of momentum and hence Snell's law. At first this seems like unnecessary formalism, but the question is: Does the inclusion of the full symmetries present lead to physics that is not given by Newtonian mechanics? We note that Newtonian mechanics deals with interactions at a point and is not particularly focused on the invariance of the trajectory rays. We argue that the symmetry approach does lead to new physics as shown in the analysis of one dimensional reflection-refraction. We have pointed this out in various previous notes, but here we argue that it is the consideration of the two symmetries in the problem, rotational and invariance along a trajectory ray which ultimately lead to $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ which may be used in continuity expressions (function and first derivative in the 1-D reflection-refraction case). This, in turn, leads to physics not described by Newtonian mechanics, but rather by quantum mechanics, which we suggest is more general.

(As an aside, we argue that linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation for a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ forces one to incorporate geometrical considerations with linear p , E and m_0 interaction variables. As a result, this seems to be a general approach in quantum mechanics.)

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell%27s_law